

Virtual Environment For Global Education: Major Possibilities And Possible Realization

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Abstract:

The current global education system, which is a crucial area for future IT, has undoubtedly encouraged developers to offer different learning systems at low cost. The learning that is presented through a combination of pedagogical technologies and integrated information, in a process of interaction between subjects and objects as virtual educational resources, is known as virtual learning in higher education. Virtual universities typically share information in large, extremely dynamic network-based environments, making formal accessing the resources in a secure manner a crucial and challenging challenge. A lot of users can collaborate and communicate in a variety of ways in interactive cyberspaces that serve as virtual environments for education, research, and daily life. They can create virtual objects like books, offices, fictional people, chalkboards, and more. Additionally, virtual environments offer the best support for information manipulation, storage, and retrieval. Virtual learning interactions are defined as a collection of fields of human activity that are dialectically connected (emotional, intellectual, figurative, cultural and social). The peculiar connection between high-quality education and ESD has shaped public perceptions of high-quality education. The Dakar Framework for Action - Education for All (UNESCO, 2000) and the Millennium Development Goals both focused on measurable learning outcomes, national standards, and competencies as the main components of quality education. The ESD perspective on quality education, on the other hand, places a focus on developing learners' skills and values with an emphasis on using them to address global sustainability challenges. The main issues discussed in this article are the use of virtual educational resources, their potential for adaptation to student subjectivity, and their implementation within the framework of university education. Virtual learning is regarded as a key element of online education. Virtual education can be thought of as an educational environment or virtual space where participants in the educational process can interact using technology.

Keywords: Virtual environment, virtual learning, pedagogical technologies, cyberspace, information storage, collaborate

Introduction:

As one might expect, in their efforts to reimagine teaching and learning, many learning environments have turned to technology. The use of technology in education has long been a major area of concern, but as our educational system undergoes rapid change, the relationship between technology and education is taking on a profoundly new meaning. New and emerging technologies are forcing a rethinking of teaching and learning while also serving as catalysts for change and innovation. A few of the skills required for all students to be successfully prepared for 21st century citizenship include creativity, global awareness, collaborative problem-solving, and self-directed learning. The traditional educational models that have evolved over the past century are simply not adequate for achieving these goals, as many educational leaders are finding out. Teachers have been forced to rethink their approaches to teaching, learning, and the environments

created to support these as a result of the learning sciences' significant advancements occurring at the same time as the outside world was changing. Not to mention, substantial advancements in educational technology have given students compelling new ways to engage with a range of materials and activities in their own self-directed learning experiences. A chance to reevaluate, re-imagines, and re-invents learning environments capable of successfully preparing each individual for life-long learning is presented by the convergence of these three events. Students have the freedom to recognize their individual talents and potentials in a good educational system. In this way, Forte explains, it's crucial to create a new classroom environment where questioning, thinking, and imagination are encouraged but not constrained in order to give students the freedom to learn. In this regard, education ought to encourage students to collaborate and pose original questions about concepts and problems from

a variety of academic disciplines. As imaginative thinkers, they make an effort to explore different possibilities and think creatively. Such a strategy is necessary for a strong academic foundation and for improving students' intelligence, which includes "soft skills" like comprehension, empathy, and communication abilities. Students with various primary learning styles can comprehend information intelligibly by using a variety of learning resources and learning materials.

Drive of technology for school change:

Systems of education undoubtedly work to advance and better the technological revolution. Due to a number of important factors, most educators and education stakeholders should consider the expanding implications and relevance of technology and technology-based school innovations. These important factors are driving some of the most significant technological implications may include: In the process of change, technology can perform several key functions, such as opening up new opportunities that can improve teaching and learning processes, especially with the capability of tailoring instruction to the needs of each individual learner, which is strongly supported by learning sciences. Technology as such is an essential and integral component of gaining access to higher order competencies, also known as 21st century skills, which are crucial for being productive in today's society. The ability to use technology effectively is one of the fundamental skills for adult life, and those who lack it may experience a new type of digital divide that could limit their ability to thrive and function in the new knowledge economy.

To support educational objectives and ensure the freedom of the teaching and learning process, current educational systems must adopt new methods, strategies, and technologies.

The New Millennium, Learners (NML), which describes the fundamental nature of learners in the modern world, has over the past few years contributed to fundamental elements. Students today, who are more and more "connected," are constantly surrounded by a constellation of digital devices. Additionally, the lives of new millennium learners are so reliant on technology that they would not be able to engage in their social and cultural practices as easily as they

do if digital media were not accessible to them 24/7.

But according to today's educational implications, students not only access, create, manage, and share knowledge in radically different ways than their teachers do quite frequently, but they also have radically different expectations for what a quality learning experience should look like, including the environment in which it should take place and the part that technology should play.

Use of technology in Education and the new digital divide:

Expecting widespread use of creative practices in education is a normal expectation given the benefits of creativity for various people at various levels. By defining concepts that are particularly significant in their eyes, creative educational practices should assist students in building their knowledge and, in the process, strengthen their sense of identity and individuality. The old digital divide may have been replaced with a new one—those who can develop the necessary ICT skills, often outside of school—because most schools have computers and internet access, but the disparity between school and home use is enormous. The potential of a virtual environment for a global education model should be based on the development of the individual and should be able to encourage flexibility, individuality, and personality development toward the following:

Tackling major barriers to inclusion

Promoting achievement

Creative and original thinking in virtual environment

Intelligent decision making capability

Improving students relationship with teachers

Acquisition of knowledge for resolving problems

Adapting flexibly to new situations

Learner-centered pedagogy which is focused on individual learners, their perspectives, experiences, backgrounds, talents, capacities, interests as well as needs with a focus on learning

Technology evolving learning environments:

For current schools operating in established systems—which are inherently constrained by established policies and structures—meeting the challenge and opportunity can be

quite challenging. These schools' desire to implement dramatic changes in practice may make new technologies and innovations crucial levers for incremental changes that may eventually result in more significant changes. Some of the web-based innovations that have spread widely throughout our world's digital culture's larger curricular frameworks and programs, and which are frequently free and simple to access, fit right in. What we refer to as "first-order" innovations are frequently used in technology-rich learning environments with the idea that combining many of these tools will result in a markedly different educational environment. Other technologies, which are more disruptive innovations, are only now beginning to realize their full potential as they emerge on the periphery of the educational landscape.

Innovation in education: the sense of urgency:

Education innovation is a hotly debated topic. Speaking with education ministers gives one the immediate impression that teachers are very resistant to change and that education systems as a whole are very reluctant to innovate. One of the most conservative social structures and areas of government policy is occasionally thought to be education. However, speaking with teachers gives one the impression that too many changes are being forced upon them without adequate consultation or the prerequisites for successfully implementing change. Innovative change has sometimes been implemented in nations without the necessary prior testing, experimentation, and evaluation. We shouldn't let the controversy distract us from the facts. Furthermore, the evidence shows that education systems are facing very serious issues that, if not addressed, could pose a serious risk to future economic growth, social advancement, and general well-being in addition to serious risks to education itself. Education systems have grown significantly since the middle of the 20th century, and human populations have never been better educated than they are now. With the belief that education is a necessary component of modernization and progress, emerging economies and developing nations are now also relentlessly expanding their educational systems. Indeed, the advantages of continuing education for both individuals and societies are still very

impressive. However, despite the fact that many policymakers might view the continued growth in numbers as the best course of action, a closer examination of the data shows that this could also put us in danger.

Linking education, creativity and entrepreneurship:

An entrepreneur is a social change agent who creates jobs for both themselves and other people. As a result, it's important to focus on enhancing entrepreneurs' skills and their education, which should raise their level of competency. Given the significance of education for entrepreneurs, it is now clear that entrepreneurship is one of the sciences with the fastest growth in undergraduate curricula in the United States and around the world. From 104 in 1975 to over 720 in 2015, the number of formal entrepreneurship programs (majors, minors, and certificates) has more than quadrupled in the last three decades. The growth of entrepreneurship courses has been exponential. Because creative thinking is crucial to the development of business ideas and is required at every stage of business development and execution, the concept of creativity is one that is frequently discussed in relation to entrepreneurship. When we discuss creativity, various definitions come to mind. However, creativity is typically described as "the generation of original ideas that are pertinent and appropriate to the situation." It entails breaking free from preconceived notions and ideas in order to discover fresh angles and approaches to problems. Increasing participation in the STEM fields has traditionally been the main goal of education policies designed to promote innovation. But recently, a broader perspective on innovation has come into existence, one that acknowledges the contribution of a wider range of abilities and disciplines. Government policy needs to take a broad view of the competencies used in the innovation process, even though STEM specialists are unquestionably important for some types of innovation, particularly technological innovation.

Theorizing quality assurance in VLEs and e-learning

The idea of teaching quality is a result of higher education becoming more standardized and consumerized. However, the idea of quality assurance in VLEs and e-learning is constantly changing, very flexible,

and widely accepted. Like "freedom" or "justice," quality is a nebulous concept that is intuitively understood but challenging to define. Due to its ambiguous characteristics, the concept is easily understood. The majority of academics believe that quality is a highly ephemeral, slippery, dynamic, multidimensional, and relative concept. There has been much iteration of what good quality means throughout the history of quality assurance. We must be aware that the ideas of "quality" and "quality assurance" are not without controversy. In order to promote entrepreneurial skills, school-level entrepreneurship education frequently uses problem-solving exercises and contextual learning based on interactive projects and games. In contrast, entrepreneurship education for young adults and students in upper secondary schools tends to focus more on imparting knowledge and honing the practical skills and knowledge required to run a business.

Opportunities & Challenges of evolving, transforming and reinventing learning environments:

According to their current context, goals, future vision, etc., each learning environment that seeks to bring about change will probably be better suited for one approach compared to the others because each of these approaches is very different and brings its own opportunities, benefits, costs, and challenges to a given situation. Since this is the least disruptive of the approaches, learning environments that seek to evolve by integrating or implementing new technologies and technology-based pedagogies with existing ones typically encounter less resistance from the existing system. The evolution approach enables each professional member of the staff to identify on ramps to new technologies in a way that is most convenient and accessible to them because the professional staff in a given context typically has a range of aptitude and comfort levels with new technologies and approaches.

New trends and issues in business and management education:

Role of B Schools:

Business schools should emphasize functional specialization as well as the finer points of general management so that students can become experts in the field.

Indian business schools need to reinvent themselves in light of the current economic climate, as well as redesign their academic programs to prepare students for those challenges.

Digital Learning:

We live in a digital age, so creating a technology-rich learning environment is still important even if none of these advantages of utilizing technology-rich instruction were true. The digital transformation is a never-ending tidal wave that is transforming every aspect of our lives, including the way we work, play, and communicate. This is not only the world in which our students are currently living, but it will also continue to develop, and the world in which they will live in the future will be digital in ways we can't even begin to fathom. Today's classrooms must at least in part be digital in order to engage students in learning processes that mirror their daily lives and to give them access to the tools and operating systems that permeate our society. The pedagogies and learning experiences that have been so far described connect with a variety of cognitive abilities and capacities, but also with digital literacy, which helps students develop crucial abilities for interacting with, consuming, and creating digital media.

Conclusion and future Directions:

Any system's chosen trajectory will need to be created and modified for its particular context, objectives, and visions. Even though the future is never certain, educational systems can have faith in the direction their generated pathway is taking if it leads to the kinds of learning that learning sciences research has shown to be effective. Technology can be a tool for systemic change in the design of the learning environment, but it can also have a micro impact on teaching and learning by generating vastly different learning experiences. The information delivered through this channel is therefore of utmost importance. Content materials like simulations, animations, and digital textbooks, also referred to as digital learning resources (DLR), have advanced significantly over the past few decades. However, we still need to develop and benchmark DLR and how they affect learning. Therefore, it is necessary to redesign the educational system and programs for women's entrepreneurship. Based on their entrepreneurial experiences,

they must develop multidimensional relationships between the course concepts and the community. As a result, engaging in creative and interactive learning should open up entirely new horizons for knowledge acquisition. The person who creates something original and turns it into an entrepreneurial activity benefits from the innovative personality development offered by this active learning approach.

We cannot wait for the obstacles and difficulties in the way of this work to disappear because there is not a perfect storm on the horizon that will make it absolutely clear the way forward. The truth is that there isn't a single, ideal approach that works in every learning environment. As long as obstacles exist, there will also be failures. The key is to embrace failures and use them as learning opportunities to recalibrate, to always be on the lookout for those barriers and plan for them as best you can, and to engage your learners on the journey of developing digital, technologically advanced virtual learning environments.

References:

1. Anderson, J. (2010). *ICT Transforming Education: Regional Guide*. Bangkok: UNESCO.
2. Anderson, J. and van Weert, T. (Eds) (2002), *Information and Communication Technology in Education: A Curriculum for Schools and Programme of Teacher Development*. Paris, UNESCO. <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001295/129538e.pdf> (Accessed 28 March, 2010)
3. Barron, B. & Darling Hammond, L. (2010). *Prospects and challenges for Inquiry-based Approaches to Learning*. In (eds), *The Nature of Learning: Using Research to Inspire Practice*. OECD Paris, France.
4. Bebell, D., & Kay, R. (2010). *One to one Computing: A Summary of the Quantitative Results from the Berkshire Wireless Learning Initiative*. *Journal of Technology, Learning, and Assessment*, 9(2) [Online journal]. Retrieved from <http://escholarship.bc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1222&context=jtla>
5. Blamire, R. (2009). *ICT Impact Data at Primary School Level: the STEPS approach*. In Scheuermann, F., & Pedro, F. (eds.), *Assessing the effects of ICT in education*, 199-211. European Union/OECD: France.
6. Centre for Research on Lifelong Learning (2009). *Conceptual Framework for Studying the Effects of ICT in Education*. Presentation by Friedrich Scheuermann at the International Expert Meeting on ICT in Education Indicators, Busan, South-Korea, 7-9 July 2009
7. Erstad, O. (2009). *Addressing the Complexity of Impact—a multilevel approach towards ICT in education*. In Scheuermann, F., & Pedro, F. (eds.), *Assessing the effects of ICT in education*, 21-38. European Union/OECD: France.
8. Fullan, M. (2011). *Whole System Reform for Innovative Teaching and Learning*. Report for the Microsoft ITL Research programme. Retrieved from <http://www.itlresearch.com/research-a-reports/2011-itl-research-findings>
9. Goodwin, B. (2011). One-to-One Laptop Programs Are No Silver Bullet. *Educational Leadership*, 68(5), 78-79.
10. Green, H., Facer, K., Rudd, T., Dillon, P., & Humphreys, P. (2005). *Personalization and Digital Technologies*. A Future lab report.
11. Groff, J. (2009). *Transforming the Systems of Public Education*. Nellie Mae Education Foundation
12. Association of American Colleges & Universities. Academic Freedom and Educational Responsibility (2006) <http://www2.winthrop.edu/acad/AcademicFreedomEducationalResponsibility.pdf>
13. Beghetto, R. A.. Does assessment kill student creativity? *The Educational Forum*, 69 (2005): 254- 263
14. Christensen, C., Johnson, C. W., & Horn, M. B “Disrupting Class: How Disruptive Innovation Will Change the Way the World Learns”, (New York: McGraw Hill. 2008)
15. Craft, A.”Creativity in schools: tensions and dilemmas”, (London: Routledge. 2005)
16. Craft, A., Cremin, T., Burnard, P., & Chappell, K “Teacher stance in creative learning: A study of progression”, *Thinking Skills and Creativity* 2(1) (2007):136–147
17. Croy, M.. “Distance education, individualization, and the demise of the

- university”, *Technology In Society* 20 (1998): 317–326.
18. Dialogue Magazine (2011). <http://www.dialogueonline.ca/freedom-conceptual-age-21st-century-learning-2003/2003/>
 19. Draves, W., How the Internet is Changing How we learn. Available from Internet: (2002) <http://kolea.kcc.hawaii.edu/tcc/tcon02/greetings/draves.html>
 20. Ferrari, A., Cachia, R., & Punie, Y... Creativity in Education and Training in the EU Member States: Fostering Creative Learning and Supporting Innovative Teaching, European Communities. (2009) http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC52374_TN.pdf
 21. Ramirez-Corona, N. et al. (2013), “Assessing metacognitive awareness during problem-solving in a kinetics and homogeneous reactor design course”, *Proceedings of the 2013 American Society for Engineering Education Annual Meeting*, Atlanta, Georgia.
 22. Rautenbach, J.V. and C. Black-Hughes (2012), “Bridging the hemispheres through the use of technology: International collaboration in social work training”, *Journal of Social Work Education*, Vol. 48/4.
 23. Resta, P. and T. Laferriere (2007), “Technology in support of collaborative learning”, *Educational Psychology Review*, Vol. 19/1, pp. 65-83.
 24. Rogers, C.P. (2011), “Shaping global citizens: Technology enhanced intercultural collaboration and transformation”, *Educational Technology*, Vol. 51/2, pp. 47-52.
 25. Shaffer, D.W. (forthcoming), “Universities of play: Games and the future of higher education”, in *Higher Education to 2030, Volume 3, Technology*, OECD Publishing, Paris.
 26. Slavin, R.E. (2010), “Co-operative learning: What makes group-work work?” in H. Dumont, D. Istance and F. Benavides (eds.), *The Nature of Learning: Using Research to Inspire Practice*, OECD Publishing, Paris <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264086487-9-en>